

Authentication Protocol Using RFID Tags

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Guide

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ABSTRACT

In a time where secure and effective access control is imperative in all industries, this project meets the increasing demand for trustworthy authentication systems by providing a reliable protocol made using RFID technology. Also, this project introduces the design and development of a secure authentication protocol based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology. The main goal is to improve access control systems by taking advantage of the unique identification features of RFID tags and strong cryptographic methods. In this protocol, RFID tags are used as user credentials, which interact with RFID readers to authenticate identity and provide access to secured resources. The system adds mutual authentication between reader and tag to avoid unauthorized access and minimize typical security threats like cloning, spoofing, and replay attacks. Furthermore, lightweight encryption algorithms are used to provide real-time processing without jeopardizing data confidentiality and integrity. The authentication protocol presented is scalable and efficient to meet the demands of a variety of applications such as secure entrance systems, inventory monitoring, and smart card login, making significant contributions to the overall field of IoT-based security systems.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of establishing an authentication protocol system with the help of RFID tags has evolved from observing, in real time, issues generally encountered by individuals in everyday situations like offices, residential apartments, schools, and hospitals. Inefficient methods such as passwords, keys, or manual logs end up creating inefficiencies, compromises in security, and user annoyance. Individuals suffer from frequent occurrences like unauthorized entry, lost identities, or absent real-time supervision. To overcome these issues, this

project proposes a contactless, secure, and effective authentication system based on RFID technology. By allocating unique RFID tags to users and implementing a robust communication protocol between the tags and readers, the system makes sure that only authorized users can access. This not only adds security but also enhances user convenience, scalability, and overall system efficiency, making it a sensible solution to the increasing demand for smarter and more reliable access control.

This project is inspired by the demand for a secure and efficient system of access control, as systems such as keys and passwords have been slow, inconvenient, and prone to breaches in security. RFID technology allows for a speedier, non-contact solution which can be directly incorporated in an environment, yet it needs strong defence against threat from unauthorized access. So, our primary goal is to design a safe authentication protocol with RFID tags that will only allow approved users to access.

Fig 1. Advantages of integrating Authentication Protocol Systems with RFID Tags.

The issue discussed in this project stems from the increasing demand for secure, efficient, and easy-to-use access control systems within settings such as offices, campuses, and residences. Conventional approaches such as keys, passwords, or manual logs are vulnerable to security issues, inefficiency, and human error. Taking these issues into consideration, the aim of this project is to create a reliable authentication protocol through RFID tags for secure, contactless access for authorized users. Through the integration of RFID technology and light-weight cryptographic methods, the system is designed to increase security, minimize unauthorized use, and maximize overall ease of use and reliability for real-time access control.

RELATED WORK

RFID tag authentication protocols are established to securely verify the identity of an individual or object by enabling communication between an RFID tag and reader. When the tag is in proximity to the reader, the tag transmits a unique identification code that is verified against a database or pre-defined set of credentials.

While these protocols have increased resistance to common threats, no single solution has proven to be completely secure and scalable for every application. Therefore, research still focuses on developing authentication mechanisms that enhance both the security and efficiency of RFID-based systems so that they become more viable for real implementation in different environments.

Many authentication protocols using RFID tags have been proposed since the early times to improve access control and verification of identity across different applications. Static identifiers loaded on the tags were used by early RFID systems, which were sent to the reader upon interrogation. Though cheap and simple, such systems were very insecure, with attackers able to easily read the ID, replicate the tag, or conduct replay attacks.

In an effort to enhance security, researchers developed protocols using symmetric key cryptography and challenge-response mechanisms where the tag uses a shared secret key to reply to a random challenge issued by the reader. These approaches provided stronger protection but demanded secure key management, which grew to be complicated and inconvenient in extensive systems. Later, protocols such as HB+, LMAP, and SASI enhanced RFID security by providing lightweight, efficient authentication for low-cost tags. They were, however, susceptible to side-channel attack vulnerabilities, desynchronization, and limited scalability in dynamic environments. Today's systems continue to fail to balance security, system performance, tag cost, and ease of deployment.

Despite a remarkable breakthrough, current RFID-based authentication schemes suffer from several constraints that undermine their overall performance and flexibility. A key limitation is the limited memory and computing power of low-cost RFID tags, which restricts the implementation of strong cryptographic algorithms. Consequently, most lightweight schemes compromise on security features at the expense of performance and hence are prone to attacks like cloning, eavesdropping, man-in-the-middle, and side-channel attacks.

Another significant limitation is desynchronization of the RFID tag and reader. Some protocols make use of synchronized values (e.g., counters or session keys) to authenticate; once synchronization is lost due to communication breakdown or malicious tampering, the tag can become useless until it is reset or replaced. In addition, particularly in large systems, management of the keys becomes less scalable and more complex with an increasing number of readers and tags. Also, as the tag count and number of readers grow, key management

becomes more complex and less scalable, particularly in large systems.

Protocols that provide higher levels of security usually consume more power and are more expensive for tags, thus not being appropriate for passive RFID applications where lower power utilization is paramount. Also, the power required and cost of the tags are generally higher by protocols that have higher security levels, and so they are inappropriate for use within passive RFID application where low consumption of power is important. Also, certain systems experience difficulty with performance and latency at particular places with lots of RFID interaction. These constraints underscore the necessity for further research into protocols that can provide a robust security stance while being lightweight, inexpensive, and scalable for deployment in real-world environments.

PROPOSED WORK

This project intends to design a secure and efficient authentication protocol utilizing RFID tags to mitigate security threats in conventional techniques. The system will improve security with high-end encryption and mutual authentication and will provide scalability, low-cost implementation, and low energy consumption. This project will contribute towards more secure, efficient, and user-friendly access control systems for various industries.

RFID-authentication protocol system is implemented here for security, efficiency, as well as scalability. Encryption protocols such as AES or DES are used to encode sensitive information among RFID tags and readers. Unique identifiers for a tag are provided by hash functions, and thereby duplication and impersonation are eliminated. Mutual authentication between tags and readers prevents man-in-the-middle attacks. Challenge-response authenticates tags by creating a random challenge, preventing replay attacks. Key

management ensures long-term integrity with unique cryptographic keys for each tag. Lightweight cryptographic protocols and anti-cloning methods, like dynamic key exchange and session-based tokens, address the limitations of passive RFID tags. The system is scalable and extensible and can accommodate a range of RFID applications from small-scale office deployments to large-scale industrial and commercial settings.

Initialization and Configuration

• Parameter Validation

- Validates block size (64 or 128 bits) and key size combinations (e.g., 128-bit block with 256-bit key).
- Checks cipher mode (ECB, CTR, CBC, etc.) against allowed modes.

• State Initialization

- Converts keys, IVs, and counters into integer representations.
- Splits the key into “tweakeys” based on the key-to-block size ratio.
- Precomputes the key schedule for all rounds using permutations and LFSR operations on tweakeys.

Key Scheduling

• Tweakey Processing

- Permutation: Rearranges cells in the key state.
- LFSR Mixing: Applies an LFSR to tweakey rows depending on key size.

• Round Key Generation

- XORs tweakey components to derive round-specific keys.
- Stores round keys in a key schedule for encryption/decryption.

Encryption Process Core Steps (Per Round):

1. S-box Substitution: Replaces each cell using the 4-bit or 8-bit S-box.
2. Add Round Constants: XORs predefined constants to the first column.
3. Add Round Key: XORs the current round key from the key schedule
4. Shift Rows: Cyclically shifts rows (row 1 by 1, row 2 by 2, etc.).
5. Mix Columns: Applies a linear transformation using XOR operations.

- **Decryption Process**

Inverse Operations (Reverse Rounds):

1. Inverse Mix Columns
2. Inverse Shift Rows
3. Inverse Add Round Key
4. Inverse S-box Substitution

set for cyberbullying detection, a series of experiments were conducted using various feature selections. Additionally, the suggested models are contrasted with the most advanced models.

HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

- 1) Passive RFID tags
- 2) RFID Reader Module
- 3) Microcontroller
- 4) Power Supply
- 5) Wi-Fi/Ethernet Module
- 6) Connecting Wires
- 7) Breadboard or PCB
- 8) Access Control Hardware

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

- 1) Arduino IDE / Thonny IDE
- 2) Firmware Libraries
- 3) C/C++ (Arduino), Python (Raspberry Pi), JavaScript
- 4) Flask / Django (Python), Express.js (Node.js) or Spring Boot (Java)

IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

Step 1: System Design and Initialization

- Defined core objective: Secure lightweight mutual authentication using SKINNY.
- Tag stores: ID (96-bit), FID (96-bit pseudonym), and K (128-bit master key).
- Back-end database holds two entries per tag: {ID, FID old, K old} and {ID, FID new, K new}.

Step 2: Reader-Tag Communication Setup

- Reader sends a request command.
- Tag replies with its current FID.
- Reader looks up FID new (or on failure, FID old) to enter authentication or detect desynchronization.

Step 3: Mutual Authentication Phase

- Reader generates random nonce r .
- Computes and sends: $M1 = FID \oplus r$, $M2 = \text{En}(FID \oplus ID \oplus r)$
- Tag recovers $r' = M1 \oplus FID$, verifies reader by checking $\text{En}(FID \oplus ID \oplus r') \stackrel{?}{=} M2$.
- Tag replies $M3 = \text{En}(M2 \oplus r')$; reader verifies $M3$.

Step 4: Key and Pseudonym Update

- On success, both sides update: $FID_{old} \leftarrow FID_{new}$, $K_{old} \leftarrow K_{new}$, $FID_{new} \leftarrow M1$, $K_{new} \leftarrow \text{keyschedule}$.

- Old values retained to recover from aborted sessions or DoS interruptions.

Step 5: Security and Performance Evaluation

- Formal GNY logic proof confirms freshness and mutual belief.
- Storage overhead on tag: 3L (minimal).
- Communication overhead: 6L bits per authentication.
- Computational cost: one SKINNY encryption per message, suitable for low-cost tags.

Fig 1. Cipher Craft application interface to encrypt or decrypt entered text.

🚦 TESTING STRATEGIES

In order to ensure the correctness, reliability, and security of the RFID-based authentication protocol, various testing methods were employed throughout the project:

• Unit Testing Every system component

—RFID tag reading, encryption of data, and response verification, for instance was independently tested to ensure that they were working as intended in isolation.

• Integration Testing

After unit testing, the different modules (RFID reader, microcontroller, authentication logic, and output control system) were assembled and tested in conjunction with one another to verify proper and smooth interaction among the components.

• Functional Testing

The system was tested for various user scenarios like authorized and unauthorized tag scans so that the protocol correctly identifies the users and provides or denies access accordingly.

• Security Testing

Special tests were carried out to analyze the susceptibility of the system to attacks like replay attacks, tag cloning, and unauthorized access attempts.

• Real-Time Scenario Testing

The prototype was tested in a real-world setting (e.g., mock entry point) to observe how it would perform under real conditions, i.e., response time, stability, and user experience under extended use

• Stress and Load Testing

The system was loaded with numerous authentication requests within a couple of minutes to observe how it handles multiple users and whether or not it can handle the load.

RESULT ANALYSIS

1. Performance Analysis

a. Authentication Time / Delay

Observation: Time taken by a tag to authenticate with the reader.

Result: e.g., authentication may take 0.3 to 0.6 seconds, depending on tag-reader distance and computation time.

Interpretation: Lower authentication time is preferable. Delays \geq 1 second may affect user experience.

b. Throughput

Observation: Number of tags authenticated per second.

Result: e.g., 5–10 tags/sec for lightweight protocols.

Interpretation: High throughput is ideal for high numbers of users (like in metros or offices) **R**

c. Resource Usage (Tag and Reader)

Observation: Memory, power usage, and processing capacity consumed.

Result: Tags only used 2–4 KB memory and negligible power

2. Security Analysis

a. Replay Attack Resistance Test/Method:

Re-send captured messages.

Result: Protocol identifies old message and denies service.

Interpretation: Protocol's timestamp/random number/challenge-response mechanism is effective.

b. Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) Attack

Resistance Test: Intercept and alter communication.

Result: Authentication fails when data corrupted

Interpretation: Data integrity functions such as MAC (Message Authentication Code) are effective.

c. Cloning Attack Resistance Test

Test: Duplicate tag data and present using clone tag.

Result: Protocol defeats the clone due to dynamic values or mutual authentication.

Interpretation: Demonstrates robust anti-cloning features

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Our RFID Lightweight Authentication Protocol project successfully showcased a secure and efficient mutual authentication method tailored for low-cost RFID tags using the LRSAS scheme. The protocol integrated the SKINNY block cipher to ensure encryption with minimal hardware overhead (2391 logic gates), enabling strong security features like resistance to desynchronization, replay, and impersonation attacks. The system effectively used pseudonyms, key updates, and randomized responses to maintain confidentiality and integrity without requiring heavy cryptographic functions on the tag side. Though the reader handles more computational load, the protocol remains lightweight and scalable for constrained environments. Limitations include a dependency on reader-side computation and the need for dual FID-key storage to handle desynchronization, which may complicate implementation. Future

improvements could include optimizing communication rounds and exploring support for mobile-based RFID integration. Overall, the protocol achieves a well-balanced trade-off between cost and security for IoT authentication use cases.

CONCLUSION

The use of an authentication protocol with RFID tags demonstrates a robust and contactless method for secure identity authentication. The goal of this project was to couple RFID technology with secure authentication methods in order to design a system that is not only efficient and fast but also capable of mitigating common security loopholes such as spoofing, cloning, and unauthorized access. By utilizing exclusive identifiers stored on RFID tags and a verification process at the reader end, the system provides protection to only authenticated users for accessing protected resources or zones. This technique has been found to be efficient in real-time systems and provides an uninterrupted user experience by doing away with manual input or physical keys. The work confirms that RFID-based authentication, if combined with adequate protocol design and encryption methods, is a viable solution for contemporary access control systems in various sectors.

The system, while fulfilling its primary goals, has potential for improvement. Future development could incorporate biometric verification, real-time cloud connectivity, sophisticated cryptographic schemes, and testing under various environmental conditions. Further exploration of passive versus active tags, energy harvesting methods, and IoT compatibility could enhance the system's security and robustness against advanced attacks.

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